

Legal Prohibition on Nuclear Weapons in Southeast Asia

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Abstract

A nuclear weapon means any explosive device capable of releasing nuclear energy in an uncontrolled manner but does not include the means, transport or delivery of such device if separable from and not an indivisible part thereof. The destructive power of nuclear weapons cannot be contained in either space or time. They have the potential to destroy all civilization and the entire ecosystem of the planet. The radiation released by a nuclear explosion would affect health, agriculture, natural resources and demography over a very wide area. Further, the use of nuclear weapons would be a serious danger to future generations. Therefore, International efforts to curb the use of nuclear weapons and prohibit their proliferation have resulted in the development of important treaties and agreements governing nuclear nonproliferation. Southeast Asian nations have also established a comprehensive legal prohibition on nuclear weapons, i.e., the Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapons Free Zone Treaty, for the maintenance of peace and security in the region. However, adherence to and implementation of nonproliferation treaties and agreements varies in the ten Southeast Asian nations of Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam.

Keywords : The seven rules of *aparivaniya*, Democracy, the *Rajadhammasangaha*

Introduction

Nuclear weapons and their proliferation remain a major threat to peace and a major challenge to the international community. Therefore, the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) was established on 29 July 1957. It is an international organization that seeks to promote the peaceful use of nuclear energy and to inhibit its use for any military purpose, including nuclear weapons. The establishment of the IAEA and the development of specific safeguards were not sufficient to prevent the non-proliferation of nuclear weapons. Consequently, the international community crowned its efforts to ensure the non-proliferation by concluding the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT). The ASEAN member states have never possessed nuclear weapons. All are compliant to the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT). The ten states that make up ASEAN have established a comprehensive legal prohibition on nuclear weapons, i.e, the Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapon-Free Zone Treaty, to preserve Southeast Asia as a Nuclear Weapons-Free Zone and free of all other weapons of mass destruction. All ASEAN countries also signed the CTBT. This paper describes the status of Nuclear Weapons nonproliferation treaties and agreements in the ten ASEAN countries: Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam.

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Definitions and Effects of Nuclear Weapons

Nuclear weapons has been defined in numerous ways in some Nuclear Weapons Free Zone Treaties, as the following definitions show.

Article 5 of the Treaty for the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons in Latin America (Treaty of Tlatelolco) provides the definition of nuclear weapon: for the purposes of this Treaty, a nuclear weapon is any device which is capable of releasing nuclear energy in an uncontrolled manner and which has a group of characteristics that are appropriate for use for warlike purposes. An instrument that may be used for the transport or propulsion of the device is not included in this definition if it is separable from the device and not an indivisible part thereof.

Article 1 (c) of the South Pacific Nuclear Free Zone Treaty (Treaty of Rarotonga) provides the definition of nuclear weapon: for the purposes of this Treaty and its Protocols, “nuclear explosive device” means any nuclear weapon or other explosive device capable of releasing nuclear energy, irrespective of the purpose for which it could be used. The term includes such a weapon or device in unassembled and partly assembled forms, but does not include the means of transport or delivery of such a weapon or device if separable from and not an indivisible part of it.

According to Article 1 (c) of the Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapons Free Zone Treaty (Bangkok Treaty), nuclear weapon means any explosive device capable of releasing nuclear energy in an uncontrolled manner but does not include the means, transport or delivery of such device if separable from and not an indivisible part thereof.

The Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons¹ was an [advisory opinion](#) delivered by the [International Court of Justice](#) (ICJ) on 8 July 1996. The request for an advisory opinion to the ICJ was presented by the [United Nations General Assembly](#) in December 1994 and accepted by the Court in January 1995.²

The ICJ, in its Nuclear Weapons Advisory Opinion, defined the “unique characteristics” of nuclear weapons: “the Court notes that nuclear weapons are explosive devices whose energy results from the fusion or fission of the atom. By its very nature, that process, in nuclear weapons as they exist today, releases not only immense quantities of heat and energy, but also powerful and prolonged radiation. According to the material before the Court, the first two causes of damage are vastly more powerful than the damage caused by other weapons, while the phenomenon of radiation is said to be peculiar to nuclear weapons. These characteristics render the nuclear weapon potentially catastrophic. The destructive power of nuclear weapons cannot be contained in either space or time. They have the potential to destroy all civilization and the entire ecosystem of the planet. The radiation released by a nuclear explosion would affect health, agriculture, natural resources and demography over a very wide area. Further, the use of nuclear weapons would be a serious danger to future generations. Ionizing radiation has the potential to damage the future environment, food and marine ecosystem, and to cause genetic defects and illness in future generations. In consequence, it is imperative for the Court to take account of the unique characteristics of nuclear weapons, and in particular their destructive capacity, their capacity to cause untold human suffering, and their ability to cause damage to generations to come.”³

Other judges in their individual decisions in the ICJ’s Nuclear Weapons case elaborated on the effects of nuclear weapons. Judge Weeramantry noted the danger of nuclear winter, whereby fires from exploded nuclear weapons could release hundreds of millions of tons of soot in the atmosphere, causing huge clouds and debris blotting out the sun and destroying agriculture. He noted that radiation from nuclear weapons is not containable in space or time and is unique as a source of “continuing danger to human health, even long after its use,” given that the half-lives of the by-products of a nuclear

¹ 1996 ICJ Rep 226.

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Court_of_Justice_advisory_opinion_on_the_Legality_of_the_Threat_or_use_of_Nuclear_Weapons.

³ Charles J. Moxley Jr., John Burroughs and Jonathan Granoff, Nuclear Weapons and Compliance with International Humanitarian Law and the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty, *Fordham International Law Journal*, Vol. 34:595, 2011, p. 603.

explosion last many thousands of years. Judge Weeramantry also noted the electromagnetic pulse as a further effect of the use of nuclear weapons, stating that this very sudden and intensive burst of energy throws all electronic devices, including communications lines such as nuclear command and control centers, out of action.¹

No one can ignore the disturbing images of the casualties of the nuclear weapons attacks on Hiroshima and Nagasaki. Hiroshima on 6 and Nagasaki on 9 August 1945 are the only times in history nuclear weapons have been employed in armed conflict.² The two bombings killed at least 129,000 people (most of whom were civilians).³

Judge Koroma noted, in the Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons advisory opinion, with respect to the atomic attacks on Hiroshima and Nagasaki: "Over 320,000 people who survived but were affected by radiation still suffer from various malignant tumours caused by radiation, including leukaemia, thyroid cancer, breast cancer, lung cancer, gastric cancer, cataracts and a variety of other after-effects. More than half a century after the disaster, they are still said to be undergoing medical examinations and treatment".⁴

As to the radiation effects of nuclear weapons, Judge Shahabuddeen stated, in the Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons advisory opinion, that "to classify these effects as being merely a byproduct is not to the point; they can be just as extensive as, if not more so than, those immediately produced by blast and heat. They cause unspeakable sickness followed by painful death, affect the genetic code, damage the unborn, and can render the earth uninhabitable. These extended effects may not have military value for the user, but this does not lessen their gravity or the fact that they result from the use of nuclear weapons. This being the case, it is not relevant for present purposes to consider whether the injury produced is a byproduct or secondary effect of such use. Nor is it always a case of the effects being immediately inflicted but manifesting their consequences in later ailments; nuclear fall-out may exert an impact on people long after the explosion, causing fresh injury to them in the course of time, including injury to future generations. The weapon continues to strike for years after the initial blow, thus presenting the disturbing and unique portrait of war being waged by a present generation on future ones - on future ones with which its successors could well be at peace".⁵

Judge Shahabuddeen further noted the extreme and indiscriminate effects of nuclear weapons: the preamble to the 1967 Treaty of Tlatelolco, Additional Protocol II of which was signed and ratified by the five nuclear weapons states, declared that the Parties are convinced "that the incalculable destructive power of nuclear weapons has made it imperative that the legal prohibition of war should be strictly observed in practice if the survival of civilization and of mankind itself is to be assured". "That nuclear weapons, whose terrible effects are suffered, indiscriminately and inexorably, by military forces and civilian population alike, constitute, through the persistence of the radioactivity they release, an attack on the integrity of the human species and ultimately may even render the whole earth uninhabitable."⁶

¹ Ibid.

² Susan Breau, "Civilian Casualties and Nuclear Weapons: The Application of the Rule of Distinction", Jonathan L. Black-Branch and Dieter Fleck (ed), *Nuclear Non-Proliferation in International Law*, Volume I, Asser Press, 2014, p. 105.

³ https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Atomic_bombings_of_Hiroshima_and_Nagasaki

⁴ Charles J. Moxley Jr., John Burroughs and Jonathan Granoff, *Nuclear Weapons and Compliance with International Humanitarian Law and the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty*, *Fordham International Law Journal*, Vol. 34:595, 2011, p. 604.

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Charles J. Moxley Jr., John Burroughs and Jonathan Granoff, *Nuclear Weapons and Compliance with International Humanitarian Law and the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty*, *Fordham International Law Journal*, Vol. 34:595, 2011, p. 605.

The Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons Advisory Opinion holds that it is a cardinal principle that a State must never make civilians an object of attack and must consequently never use weapons that are incapable of distinguishing between civilian and military targets.¹

Judge Weeramantry's opinion is based on the proposition that the use or threat of use of nuclear weapons is illegal in any circumstances whatsoever. It violates the fundamental principles of international law, and represents the very negation of the humanitarian concerns which underlie the structure of humanitarian law. It offends conventional law and, in particular, the Geneva Gas Protocol of 1925, and Article 23(a) of the Hague Regulations of 1907. It contradicts the fundamental principle of the dignity and worth of the human person on which all law depends. It endangers the human environment in a manner which threatens the entirety of life on the planet."²

In short, based on its deliberations, the ICJ has stated that, nuclear weapons caused death and destruction; induced cancers, leukaemia, keloids and related afflictions; caused gastrointestinal, cardiovascular and related afflictions; continued, for decades after its use, to induce the health-related problems mentioned above; damaged the environmental rights of future generations; caused congenital deformities, mental retardation and genetic damage; carried the potential to cause a nuclear winter; contaminated and destroyed the food chain; imperilled the ecosystem; produced lethal levels of heat and blast; produced radiation and radioactive fallout; produced a disruptive electromagnetic pulse; produced social disintegration; imperilled all civilization; threatened human survival; wreaked cultural devastation; spanned a time range of thousands of years; threatened all life on the planet; irreversibly damaged the rights of future generations; exterminated civilian populations; damaged neighbouring States; and produced psychological stress and fear syndromes – as no other weapons do.³

The use of nuclear weapons represents an unprecedented threat to the viability of the global environment. The effects of the use of nuclear weapons will never be confined to a single nation State; its effects will be transnational.⁴ Even a small use of nuclear weapons would still constitute a "major war." Therefore, questions related to the role and effects of nuclear weapons remain highly relevant.⁵

Additionally, the testing of nuclear weapons has demonstrated that explosions contaminate food and those in or near the oceans contaminate ocean resources such as fish. However, the central fact about the destruction of the environment is that it leads to the destruction on a universal basis of the right to life upon which all other human rights depend.⁶

Nuclear weapons and their proliferation remain a major threat to peace and a major challenge to the international community. Some States of the world in an endeavor to show their power and strength compete in the production of nuclear weapons which, when used, can easily kill people and all living creatures and cause the immediate destruction of buildings and the entire global environment. In fact even the explosions accompanying the testing of nuclear weapons give rise to a variety of dangers ranging from causing air pollution and water pollution to adversely affecting human health. Therefore, the people of the world have called for the abolishment of nuclear weapon production and have always objected to the testing and exploding of nuclear weapons. In the Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons Advisory Opinion, the ICJ indicated that the use of nuclear weapons violates international law and maintained that it is an important principle that a State must never make civilians an object

¹ Susan Breau, "Civilian Casualties and Nuclear Weapons: The Application of the Rule of Distinction", Jonathan L. Black-Branch and Dieter Fleck (ed), Nuclear Non-Proliferation in International Law, Volume I, Asser Press, 2014, p. 106.

² Summaries of Judgments, Advisory Opinions and Orders of the International Court of Justice, 1992-1996, United Nations Publication, 1998, p. 102.

³ Summaries of Judgments, Advisory Opinions and Orders of the International Court of Justice, 1992-1996, United Nations Publication, 1998, p. 102.

⁴ <http://www.worldacademy.org/files/Nuclear>.

⁵ Sarah J. Diehl and James Clay Moltz, Nuclear Weapons and Non-Proliferation, A Reference Handbook, Second edition, ABC-CLIO press, 2008, p. 41.

⁶ <http://www.worldacademy.org/files/Nuclear>.

of attack and must consequently never use weapons that are incapable of distinguishing between civilian and military targets. Any use of nuclear weapons causes injury to human health, damages the environment and destroys all the values of civilization. Therefore, International law permits countries to use nuclear technologies for peaceful purposes but prohibits the proliferation of nuclear materials and technologies for non-peaceful uses. International efforts to curb the use of nuclear weapons and prohibit their proliferation have resulted in the development of important treaties and agreements governing nuclear nonproliferation.

The Status of Nuclear Non-proliferation Treaties in the ASEAN States

The ASEAN member states have never possessed nuclear weapons. All are compliant to the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT). The 10 states that make up ASEAN have established a comprehensive legal prohibition on nuclear weapons, i.e, the Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapon-Free Zone Treaty (the Bangkok Treaty), for the maintenance of peace and security in the region. All ASEAN countries also signed the CTBT.

Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT)

The NPT is the only internationally-binding agreement that provides a global barrier to the spread of nuclear weapons. The treaty was concluded in July 1968 and entered into force in March 1970. As of 2017, there were 191 State Parties to the treaty. Only three States - India, Israel, and Pakistan - have never adhered to the Treaty. Only one State - North Korea - has announced its withdrawal from the NPT. The NPT defines a nuclear-weapon state (NWS) as a state that manufactured and exploded a nuclear weapon or other nuclear device prior to 1 January, 1967. These states are China, France, Russia, the United Kingdom, and the United States. All other states are non-nuclear-weapon states (NNWS) under the Treaty.¹

The NPT has three 'pillars': non-proliferation, disarmament and peaceful use of nuclear energy. The non-proliferation pillar means that each of the five NWS agrees not to transfer 'nuclear weapons or other nuclear explosive devices' to a non-nuclear weapon State ('NNWS') (Article I NPT). NNWS parties to the NPT agree not to obtain nuclear weapons (Article II NPT),² and accept IAEA safeguards to verify that their nuclear activities serve only peaceful purposes (Article III NPT).³

The disarmament pillar in Article VI NPT urges all State Parties 'to pursue negotiations in good faith on effective measures relating to cessation of the nuclear arms race at an early date and to nuclear disarmament, and on a treaty on general and complete disarmament under strict and effective international control'.⁴

The third pillar in Article IV NPT not only states that the NPT does not affect 'an inalienable right' of all parties to develop peaceful applications of nuclear power, but also encourages provision of assistance to such development, especially to the NNWS.⁵

These pillars are interrelated and mutually reinforcing. An effective nonproliferation regime whose members comply with their obligations provides an essential foundation for progress on disarmament and makes possible greater cooperation on the peaceful use of nuclear energy. With the right to access the benefits of peaceful nuclear technology comes the responsibility of nonproliferation. Progress on disarmament reinforces efforts to strengthen the

¹ <http://www.state.gov/documents/organization>.

² Vitaly Fedchenko, Nuclear Energy, Peaceful Uses, Max Planck Encyclopedia of Public International Law, Oxford University Press, 2009, p. 4.

³ <http://www.state.gov/documents/organization>.

⁴ Vitaly Fedchenko, Nuclear Energy, Peaceful Uses, Max Planck Encyclopedia of Public International Law, Oxford University Press, 2009, p. 4.

⁵ Ibid.

nonproliferation regime and to enforce compliance with obligations, thereby also facilitating peaceful nuclear cooperation.¹

Nevertheless, Article I obliges NWS to commit to restrictions on “horizontal proliferation” which is restrictions on the spread of nuclear weapons to States which do not already possess them. However, such obligation by the NWS is voluntary and cannot be enforced under the NPT which lacks a formal mechanism to compel compliance and punish non-compliance. Article III of the NPT requires each NNWS to accept safeguards as set forth in an agreement with IAEA, “on all special fissile material whether it is being produced, processed or used in all peaceful nuclear activities within the territory” of a State party. However, this obligation is only imposed on NNWS. The IAEA safeguards do not extend to the NWS. This is a real weakness in the NPT rules.

The NPT is in force in every ASEAN state. Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, the Philippines, and Singapore signed the treaty the year it came into effect or shortly thereafter and they all ratified it in the 1970s. Cambodia and Thailand acceded to it in 1972. Brunei Darussalam and Vietnam acceded only in 1985 and 1982, respectively. By 1992, when Myanmar completed its accession procedure, all ASEAN states were NPT parties. Cambodia’s and the Philippines’ commitment to the NPT is also reinforced by their respective constitutions. Article 54 of Cambodia’s constitution, which was enacted in 1993, states that “The manufacturing, use, storage of nuclear, chemical, or biological weapons shall be absolutely prohibited.” Similarly, Section 8 of the Philippines’s constitution, which was enacted in 1987, declares that “The Philippines, consistent with the national interest, adopts and pursues a policy of freedom from nuclear weapons in its territory.”²

ASEAN States thereby have shown to the world that it supports and encourages the non proliferation of nuclear weapons and nuclear weapons disarmament.

Comprehensive Nuclear-Test-Ban Treaty (CTBT)

The Comprehensive Nuclear Test Ban Treaty (CTBT) bans all nuclear explosions everywhere, by everyone, and for all times.³ The Comprehensive Nuclear-Test-Ban Treaty (CTBT) obligates its parties “not to carry out any nuclear weapon test explosion or any other nuclear explosion.” It is meant to limit both the development by nuclear-armed states of new or more powerful weapons and the spread of nuclear weapon technology to new states. Even though states may be able to manufacture rudimentary atomic weapons without testing, it is likely to be impossible for them to develop the more complex and more powerful thermonuclear weapons, which require testing. The CTBT was opened to signature in September 1996. That same year, the Preparatory Commission for the CTBT Organization (CTBTO) was set up in Vienna: it is an interim organization tasked with building up the verification regime of the treaty in preparation for its entry into force and with promoting the treaty’s universality.⁴ As of September 2016, 183 states had signed it and 166 had ratified it. All ASEAN countries signed the CTBT the year it was open to signature or shortly thereafter. As of September 2016, however, only nine had ratified it. Thailand has not yet ratified it.⁵ Myanmar signed the Comprehensive Nuclear Test Ban Treaty (CTBT) on 25 November 1996 and ratified it in 2016. By ratifying the Comprehensive Nuclear Test Ban Treaty, the government of Myanmar has shown to the world that it supports and encourages the non proliferation of nuclear weapons and nuclear weapons disarmament.⁶

Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapons Free Zone Treaty (Bangkok Treaty)

¹ <http://www.state.gov/documents/organization>.

² David Santoro, *The Association of Southeast Asian Nations in the Global Safety, Security and Nonproliferation Regimes, Issues & Insights* Vol. 12 – No. 3, Honolulu, Hawaii, May 2012, p.2.

³ <http://www.ctbto.org/press-centre/press-release-myanmar-ratifies-the-comprehensive-nuclear-test-ban-treaty/>

⁴ David Santoro, *The Association of Southeast Asian Nations in the Global Safety, Security and Nonproliferation Regimes, Issues & Insights* Vol. 12 – No. 3, Honolulu, Hawaii, May 2012, p.4.

⁵ <https://www.ctbto.org/the-treaty/status-of-signature-and-ratification/>

⁶ *The Mirror Daily Newspaper*, September 23 2016.

The Treaty of Bangkok evolved from the earlier 1971 Zone of Peace, Freedom and Neutrality in South-East Asia (ZOPFAN) initiative of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) advanced by the five founding members (Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore and Thailand). This was in response to concern about NWS military bases and nuclear weapon transit by plane and sea in the region. When the NWSs with military bases in the region - the Russian Federation in Vietnam and the United States in the Philippines - closed their bases, implementation of the zone became more feasible politically.¹

The Bangkok Treaty establishes the Southeast Asia Nuclear-Weapon-Free Zone (SEANWFZ). It prohibits its states parties to develop, manufacture or otherwise acquire, possess, or have control over nuclear weapons; station or test nuclear weapons anywhere inside or outside the treaty zone; take any action to assist or encourage the manufacture or acquisition of any nuclear explosive device by any state; provide source or special fissionable materials or equipment to any NNWS or any NWS unless subject to safeguards agreements with the IAEA; and dump radioactive wastes and other radioactive matter at sea anywhere within the treaty zone as well as the dumping of radioactive wastes and other radioactive matter by anyone in territorial sea of states parties. The treaty zone covers the territories, continental shelves, and exclusive economic zones of the ten ASEAN countries. Verification is achieved through reports by members and the exchange of information, and through the application of IAEA safeguards. The treaty also provides for a Commission for SEANWFZ to oversee implementation and ensure compliance with the various provisions. Finally, the treaty includes protocols under which the five NWS undertake to respect SEANWFZ, not to contribute to any act which violates it, and not to use or threaten to use nuclear weapons against any state party or within the treaty zone.²

The Bangkok Treaty was opened for signature in December 1995 and entered into force in March 1997. All ASEAN states signed the treaty in 1995. All ratified it within the next two years, with the exception of the Philippines, which only deposited its instrument of ratification in 2001. Since the late 1990s, one of the primary nonproliferation objectives of the ASEAN Secretariat has been ratification of the protocols by the five NWS: none of them have signed up to them, mainly because the treaty extends the exclusive economic zones of the states parties, potentially restricting the free passage of military ships through the region. In 2011, however, as part of its efforts as ASEAN chair, Indonesia pressed heavily for the acceptance of the Bangkok Treaty protocols by the five NWS. In October 2011, Indonesia and the NWS co-sponsored a resolution in support of the treaty in the UN General Assembly. One month later, ASEAN announced that it had negotiated a tentative agreement with the NWS. Although the specifics of this agreement remain unknown, all parties have referred to the negotiations as a success. It is unclear, however, how domestic ratification procedures would play out in the NWS.³

Nevertheless, the Bangkok Treaty strengthens the nonproliferation commitments of the ASEAN group and confirms the right of the States Parties to use of nuclear energy for peaceful purposes. It also prevents NWSs from again stationing nuclear-capable forces at military bases in the region. It is the main treaty relating to the comprehensive legal prohibition on nuclear weapons in Southeast Asia.

International Nuclear Safeguards Regime in the ASEAN States

The international nuclear safeguards regime is designed to assess whether a country's nuclear activities are peaceful. To do this the regime relies on specific agreements, which stipulate the responsibilities of states and International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA).

International Atomic Energy Agency Membership

¹ Michael Hamal-Green, "Peeling the orange: Regional Paths to a Nuclear-Weapon-Free World", Disarmament Forum, United Nations, 2011, p. 7.

² David Santoro, *The Association of Southeast Asian Nations in the Global Safety, Security and Nonproliferation Regimes, Issues & Insights Vol. 12 – No. 3*, Honolulu, Hawaii, May 2012, p.4.

³ David Santoro, *The Association of Southeast Asian Nations in the Global Safety, Security and Nonproliferation Regimes, Issues & Insights Vol. 12 – No. 3*, Honolulu, Hawaii, May 2012, p.4.

The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) was established in Vienna in July 1957. According to the IAEA Statute, the IAEA has three main 'pillars'(areas of work): it helps States to upgrade their nuclear safety and security; assists States in developing nuclear science and technology applications; and safeguards the nuclear material to verify that it is not used for military purposes, including nuclear weapons. By February 2016, the IAEA had 168 member states.

All ASEAN countries are members of the IAEA, with the exception of Brunei Darussalam, in large part due to its lack of nuclear infrastructure. Most of them joined the Agency in the late 1950s and 1960s. Laos, however, only joined in 2011. Cambodia was a member of the IAEA between 1958 and 2003, when it withdrew because he had been in arrears with its dues for several years; it joined again in 2009 after concluding a dues repayment plan with the IAEA.¹

Comprehensive Safeguards Agreements

The CSA is a bilateral agreement between a state and IAEA. In accordance with Article III of the NPT, each NNWS is required to conclude a Comprehensive Safeguards Agreement (CSA) with the IAEA to enable the application of safeguards on all source and special fissionable material in all peaceful nuclear activities. The CSA is called full-scope safeguards because it is applied throughout the country. Safeguards measures, including on-site inspections, visits, and on-going monitoring and evaluation, enable the IAEA to verify that a state is living up to its nonproliferation obligations. The CSA limits the scope of IAEA verification to declared nuclear material and activities.

Full-scope safeguards are in force in every ASEAN state. Seven of the ten ASEAN countries concluded these agreements in the 1970s and 1980s. Myanmar, Cambodia, and Laos concluded theirs in the 1990s and they came into force in April 1995, December 1999, and April 2001, respectively.²

Small Quantities Protocol

For states which have only very small quantities of nuclear material, the CSA allows them to conclude a Small Quantities Protocol (SQP) which holds in abeyance most of the operative provisions of the IAEA's verification tools. Over time, however, concerns have been raised because an SQP makes it difficult for the IAEA to evaluate a state's nuclear program (or lack thereof) or to confirm that a state meets or continues to meet the conditions required for having an SQP. This has led the IAEA Board of Governors to approve in September 2005 a modified SQP text that reduces the number of safeguards measures held in abeyance and makes an SQP unavailable to states with existing or planned facilities. Since then, states that already have an SQP have been encouraged to amend it in line with the new provisions, and any state that signs a safeguards agreement with an SQP after September 2005 must accept the modified SQP version.³

As of May 2017, five of the ten ASEAN countries had an SQP in force: Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar, and Singapore. Only Singapore and Cambodia, however, have adopted the modified SQP text in March 2008 and July 2014. Although Brunei, Cambodia, Laos and Myanmar do not pose nuclear proliferation risks, their nonproliferation credentials would be burnished if they adopted the modified SQP text.

Additional Protocol

The Additional Protocol (AP) is a legal agreement that grants the IAEA complementary inspection authority to the one provided in underlying CSA. Its goal is to enable the IAEA

¹ David Santoro, *The Association of Southeast Asian Nations in the Global Safety, Security and Nonproliferation Regimes, Issues & Insights Vol. 12 – No. 3*, Honolulu, Hawaii, May 2012, p.6.

² Ibid.

³ David Santoro, *The Association of Southeast Asian Nations in the Global Safety, Security and Nonproliferation Regimes, Issues & Insights Vol. 12 – No. 3*, Honolulu, Hawaii, May 2012, p.6.

inspectorate to provide assurance about both declared and possible undeclared activities, i.e., allowing it to verify not only the correctness, but also the completeness of state declarations. Under the AP, the IAEA is also granted expanded rights of access to information and sites. In other words, an AP considerably boosts the IAEA's ability to detect illicit nuclear activities, including those with no connection to the fuel cycle.

Among the ASEAN countries, only five have an AP in force: Cambodia, Indonesia, the Philippines, Singapore and Vietnam. Indonesia is the first ASEAN country to have had an AP in force (September 1999). In 2003, it became one of the few countries with which the IAEA was able to implement an "integrated safeguards" approach of combining safeguards tools in the most effective and cost-efficient way; for Indonesia, this included upgraded surveillance systems and short-notice inspections. Although the Philippines signed an AP in September 1997, it did not enter into force before February 2010 because members of the Senate, who are focused predominantly on domestic issues, refused to give priority to what they considered a complicated international text of little positive impact on Filipinos' lives. Similarly, it took two and a half years for Singapore to bring into force the AP it had signed with the IAEA in September 2005: it brought it into force in March 2008.¹ Cambodia and Vietnam brought it into force in April 2015 and September 2012. Malaysia, Thailand, Laos and Myanmar have all signed an AP, but as of May 2017, they had yet to ratify it. In the region, the one AP holdout state is Brunei Darussalam.

Myanmar

Myanmar joined the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) in 1957, and participated in a number of IAEA technical cooperation projects in isotope applications for agriculture beginning in the 1960s.

Myanmar became a non-nuclear weapon State Party to the Treaty on the Non-proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT) in 1992.² The NPT is a landmark international treaty whose objective is to prevent the spread of nuclear weapons and weapons technology, to promote cooperation in the peaceful uses of nuclear energy and to further the goal of achieving nuclear disarmament and general and complete disarmament.³

Myanmar signed the Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapon-Free Zone Treaty (Bangkok Treaty) in 1995, committing not to develop nuclear weapons.

The country signed a Comprehensive Safeguards Agreement with the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) in 1995.⁴ In accordance with Article III of the NPT, each NNWS is required to conclude a Comprehensive Safeguards Agreement (CSA) with the IAEA to enable the application of safeguards on all source and special fissionable material in all peaceful nuclear activities. The CSA is called full-scope safeguards because it is applied throughout the country.⁵

Myanmar signed a Small Quantities Protocol with the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) in 1995.⁶ For states which have only very small quantities of nuclear material, the CSA allows them to conclude a Small Quantities Protocol (SQP) which holds in abeyance most of the operative provisions of the IAEA's verification tools.⁷

¹ David Santoro, *The Association of Southeast Asian Nations in the Global Safety, Security and Nonproliferation Regimes, Issues & Insights Vol. 12 – No. 3*, Honolulu, Hawaii, May 2012, p.7.

² <http://www.nti.org/learn/countries/myanmar/>

³ <https://www.un.org/disarmament/wmd/nuclear/npt/>

⁴ <http://www.nti.org/learn/countries/myanmar/>

⁵ David Santoro, *The Association of Southeast Asian Nations in the Global Safety, Security and Nonproliferation Regimes, Issues & Insights Vol. 12 – No. 3*, Honolulu, Hawaii, May 2012, p. 6.

⁶ <http://www.nti.org/learn/countries/myanmar/>

⁷ David Santoro, *The Association of Southeast Asian Nations in the Global Safety, Security and Nonproliferation Regimes, Issues & Insights Vol. 12 – No. 3*, Honolulu, Hawaii, May 2012, p. 6.

Myanmar signed an Additional Protocol with the IAEA on 17 September 2013. The Additional Protocol is a legal document that, when concluded with States with Comprehensive Safeguards Agreements (CSAs), equips the IAEA with important additional measures that provide for broader access to information about the State's nuclear programme, increased physical access by IAEA inspectors and improved administrative arrangements. The implementation of an Additional Protocol significantly increases the IAEA's ability to verify the peaceful use of all nuclear material in States with CSAs in force.¹

Myanmar also signed the Comprehensive Nuclear Test Ban Treaty (CTBT) on 25 November 1996 and ratified it in 2016. As of 22 September 2016, 183 States have signed the Treaty and 166 States have ratified it. By ratifying the Comprehensive Nuclear Test Ban Treaty, the government of Myanmar has shown to the world that it supports and encourages the non proliferation of nuclear weapons and nuclear weapons disarmament.² The Comprehensive Nuclear Test Ban Treaty (CTBT) bans all nuclear explosions everywhere, by everyone, and for all times.³

On 1 December 2014, Myanmar became the 171st member nation to join the Biological and Toxin Weapons Convention (BTWC). The Biological and Toxin Weapons Convention (BTWC) was the first multilateral treaty categorically banning a class of weapon. The treaty prohibits the development, stockpile, production, or transfer of biological agents and toxins of "types and quantities" that have no justification for protective or peaceful use. Furthermore, the treaty bans the development of weapons, equipment, or delivery systems to disseminate such agents or toxins. As of November 4, 2016, it had 173 State Parties.⁴

Myanmar became the 191st State Party to the Chemical Weapons Convention (CWC) in 2015. The Chemical Weapons Convention prohibits the production, development, possession, stockpiling, transfer and use of chemical weapons.⁵

Myanmar ratified the Convention on the Physical Protection of Nuclear Material (CPPNM) and the Convention on Nuclear Safety (CNS) on 6 December 2016. While Myanmar stands for complete nuclear disarmament, it supports the peaceful application of nuclear energy. Accordingly its ratification to the said conventions reflects Myanmar's great emphasis on nuclear safety and security.⁶

In another gesture expressing the government's views on the subject, "the Ministry for Foreign Affairs of the Government of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar expressed its deep concern on the testing and detonation of a hydrogen bomb by the Democratic People's Republic of Korea (DPRK) on 6 January 2016. It also stated that the test was a "violation of the relevant United Nations Security Council Resolutions" and that it "undermined the international non-proliferation regime and increased tension in the Korean Peninsula". The proclamation also reaffirmed Myanmar's commitment to nuclear weapons disarmament and non-proliferation and stated that as a Party to the Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapon-Free Zone, it was making every effort towards achieving a world free of nuclear weapons and that Myanmar called upon and encouraged the Democratic People's Republic of Korea to abide by the United Nations Security Council Resolution concerned.⁷

With regard to domestic legislation, the State Peace and Development Council enacted the Myanmar Atomic Energy Law on 8th June 1998. It consists of 39 sections in 14 chapters. Atomic Energy Law primarily provided for ensuring safety in the utilization of radioactive material and irradiation apparatus.⁸

¹ <https://www.iaea.org/newscenter/news/myanmar-signed-additional-protocol-iaea>.

² The Mirror Daily Newspaper, September 23 2016.

³ <http://www.ctbto.org/press-centre/press-release-myanmar-ratifies-the-comprehensive-nuclear-test-ban-treaty/>

⁴ <http://www.nti.org/learn/treaties-and-regimes/convention-prohibition-development-producton-and-stockpiling-bacteriological-biological-and-toxin-weapons-btwc/>

⁵ <https://www.opcw.org/news/article>.

⁶ <http://www.mofa.gov.mm>.

⁷ The Mirror Daily Newspaper, January 14 2016.

⁸ Dr. Moe Min Htwe, Regional Workshop on Development of National Policy and Strategy for Radioactive Waste Management, Vienna, Austria, 24-28 March 2014. (<https://gnsn.iaea.org/wasteManagement>)

In June 4, 2014, the Anti-Terrorism Law is enacted by the Pyidaungsu Hluttaw in Myanmar. In this law there are totally 72 sections in 19 chapters and many provisions relating to nuclear terrorism. It includes, inter alia, the definitions on nuclear weapon, device (any nuclear explosive device or any radioactive material dispersal or radiation-emitting device), nuclear material, radioactive material, nuclear facility and international nuclear transport in Sections 3 (l) (m) (n) (o) (p) (q) whilst Sections 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25 and 26 contain the offences with regard to nuclear material, radioactive material, nuclear facility and prevention and suppression of biological, chemical and nuclear weapons. Among these sections, Sections 50 (c) (d) (e) (f) of this Law states punishments relating to nuclear terrorism. According to Section 50, if a person commits the following:

- (a) offence relating to nuclear material, radioactive material, biological, chemical and nuclear weapons
- (b) offence relating to nuclear facility
- (c) offence relating to import, export, transport and transfer of nuclear material, radioactive material and material on nuclear facility
- (d) offence relating to nuclear terrorism, he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term which may extend from a minimum of ten years to a maximum term of imprisonment for life and shall also be liable to fine.

The Myanmar Anti-Terrorism Law provides penalties in line with the gravity of such crimes. It aims to halt terrorism, to make such offences punishable by appropriate penalties that take into account their grave nature. The prevention and suppression of nuclear terrorism comprises halting nuclear weapon proliferation and access to nuclear material, radioactive material, chemical, biological and nuclear weapons stemming from the accidental or intentional use.

Section 26 (b) (c) of this Law contain provisions which prohibit the forceful use or the threat to use any nuclear or radioactive material, or a nuclear facility intended for peaceful uses, as mentioned below:

"Any attempt to forcefully use or threaten to use nuclear material, radioactive material or a nuclear facility intended for peaceful uses, shall not be held permissible by the Law.

There shall not be any harm caused to efforts to strengthen the protection of nuclear material, radioactive material, a nuclear facility or the transport of nuclear technology for peaceful uses in line with international conventions."

Furthermore, to counter and prevent incidents of nuclear terrorism, Section 57 prescribe the exercise of international cooperation between States and Section 59 and 60 call for the extradition of offenders.

By signing the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty (NPT) and the Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapon-Free Zone Treaty and by enacting the Myanmar Atomic Energy Law, it can be said that Myanmar is committed to a policy of nuclear weapons disarmament and non-proliferation.

In the nuclear nonproliferation domain, all ASEAN countries are states parties to the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT) and the Southeast Asia Nuclear-Weapon-Free-Zone Treaty (Bangkok Treaty). ASEAN States thereby have shown to the world that it supports and encourages the non proliferation of nuclear weapons and nuclear weapons disarmament. Moreover, Cambodia's and the Philippines's commitment to the NPT is reinforced by their respective constitutions. The other ASEAN states, like the Philippines and Cambodia should also reinforce their commitments to the NPT through appropriate legal measures. All ASEAN states signed the CTBT. However, only nine had ratified it. Thailand has not yet ratified it and many still need to enhance their safeguards agreements with the IAEA in order to improve confidence levels that they are not engaged

in illicit activities. Therefore, adherence to and implementation of nonproliferation treaties and agreements varies in Southeast Asia.

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Treaties and Agreements

Additional Protocol

Comprehensive Nuclear Test Ban Treaty

Comprehensive Safeguards Agreements

Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons

Small Qualities Protocol

Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapons Free Zone Treaty

Statute of the International Atomic Energy Agency

Appendix

Status of the Principal Nuclear Nonproliferation Treaties in ASEAN						
State	Nuclear Nonproliferation Treaty (NPT 1968)		Comprehensive Nuclear-Test-Ban Treaty (CTBT 1996)		Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapon-Free-Zone Treaty (Bangkok Treaty 1995)	
	Signed	Ratified	Signed	Ratified	Signed	Ratified
Brunei		1985(a)	1997	2013	1995	1996
Cambodia		1972(a)/1987(a)	1996	2000	1995	1997
Indonesia	1970	1979	1996	2012	1995	1997
Laos	1968	1970	1997	2000	1995	1996
Malaysia	1968	1970	1998	2008	1995	1996
Myanmar		1992(a)	1996	2016	1995	1996
Philippines	1968	1972	1996	2001	1995	2001
Singapore	1970	1976	1999	2001	1995	1997
Thailand		1972(a)	1996		1995	1997
Vietnam		1982(a)	1996	2006	1995	1996

IAEA Membership and Status of Nuclear Safeguards in ASEAN				
State	IAEA Membership	Small Quantities Protocol (SQP)	Comprehensive Safeguards Agreements (CSA)	Additional Protocol (AP)
Brunei		December 2005	In Force: Nov. 1987	
Cambodia	2009	Amended: July 2014	In Force: Dec. 1999	Inforce: April 2015
Indonesia	1957		In Force: July 1980	In force: Sept.1999
Laos	2011	December 2005	In Force: April 2001	Signed: Nov. 2014
Malaysia	1969		In Force: Feb.1972	Signed: Nov. 2005
Myanmar	1957	December 2005	In Force: April 1995	Signed: Sept. 2013
Philippines	1958		In Force: Oct.1974	In force: Feb. 2010
Singapore	1967	Amended : March 2008	In Force: Oct. 1977	Inforce:March2008
Thailand	1957		In Force: May 1974	Signed: Sept. 2005
Vietnam	1957		In Force: Feb.1990	In force: Sept. 12